

Practitioner-oriented consulting for agroforestry systems in Austria

Introduction

Under certain conditions, contemporary agroforestry systems can be an economically and ecologically interesting way of optimizing land use for future (climate change-related) challenges, because they increase the productivity of an area without placing greater demands on natural resources. The OG “Agroforestry in Austria” promoted agroforestry systems in Austria by means of establishing demonstration sites and generating practical knowledge.

Practitioner-oriented consulting

The OG created a novel consulting service for agroforestry in Austrian agriculture. In Austria, the existing consulting services in agriculture did not meet the demand of farmers interested in agroforestry to provide them with guidance and support. When the OG started, there was no state-based consulting for identification of suitable agroforestry systems and their implementation. The OG met this demand and created learning opportunities for the multiple actors involved: six farmers in Upper- und Lower Austria, who were willing to implement site-adapted agroforestry systems, the Lower Austria's Chamber for Agriculture, and various experts in agroforestry. Establishing the demonstration sites benefited from practitioners' interest in and readiness for the topic.

Lower Austria is one of eight Austrian provinces (plus Vienna). It is home to 1.7 Mio people and covers the largest territory (almost 20.000 km²) among Austrian provinces. The environmental pressure on the arable area is high.

Lessons learned

The OG raised awareness for agroforestry among practitioners and in administrations, made concrete how different systems are implemented in practice, and the (potential) benefits which they delivered.

What went well? There was great diversity of agroforestry systems in the project, which allowed to generate a broad range of information material and support within the three-year project duration.

What should be improved? Involve more farms as participants for demonstration sites to increase opportunities for experimentation and development.

Figure 1: Practitioner-oriented consulting at demonstration site (© Markut Theresia/FIBL)

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Further information

<https://agroforst-oesterreich.at/projekte/>

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